

CLINICAL AND THERAPEUTIC FEATURES OF CHRONIC ENDOMETRITIS

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Abstract. *Chronic endometrial cancer often develops in the acute form of the disease. Most often, more advanced forms of inflammation that are not cleared or incorrectly defined are poured. This pathology is based on two forms of the disease. Acute inflammation. Chronic endometritis. Symptoms and treatment will vary depending on the stage of the disease.*

Keywords: *disease, inflammation, various gynecological manipulations, abortion, uterus, childbirth, sexually transmitted infections, chronic endometritis, personal hygiene.*

SYMPTOMS OF INFLAMMATION OF THE UTERUS

As mentioned above, symptoms of chronic endometritis and treatment are different. It all depends on what triggers its appearance. We will consider this question as fully as possible in the US.

IRREGULAR MENSTRUAL PERIOD

Due to the inflammatory process of the endometrium, the structure changes for progression. very thin - in other places it can be thick in some places. Because of this process, a woman may complain of late heavy periods. Or talk about it during the cycle when it was observed to identify the genitals.

PAIN AND FEVER

It can be a woman's inflammatory process, with an increase in temperature, which can cause a crushing pain in the lower abdomen. In most cases, these symptoms occur when the chronic form of the mother is taken after acute inflammation of the inner layer.

Also, a woman with chronic endometritis may feel unpleasant pain during intercourse. It was found that the uterus was enlarged and inflamed.

INFERTILITY OR INFANT FAILURE

Many women ask, "If there is chronic endometritis, it is possible to get pregnant." Experienced gynecologists claim that fertilization of the maternal layer can occur during inflammation. However, the seed the inner layer of the soft egg will not be fixed properly.

In some cases, according to the circumstances, couples should resort to artificial insemination in the uterine cavity and subsequent transfer of eggs. It should be noted that chronic endometritis and tube babies are absolutely incompatible. Neither a qualified person will undertake to carry out the procedure without previous treatment.

MEDICAL CORRECTION

Chronic symptoms of endometritis are present and the treatment should be chosen accordingly, depending on what. In many cases, it is determined by the main strategy, which can be supplemented by various preparations and treatments.

ANTIBACTERIALS

Accumulation and proliferation of microorganisms cause inflammation, for treatment, antibacterial agents are prescribed, for example, the drug "Metronidazole", "Doxycycline" from the tablet, "Naxodgin" and others. If a woman is found to have a sexually transmitted disease, then her action is increased, for example, the drugs "Vilprofen", "Amoxicillin" are prescribed appropriate drugs aimed at eliminating the infection.

If the fair sex is a regular partner, it should also be treated accordingly. Otherwise, after restoring another part of the microorganisms, everything will be the same again.

PAIN RELIEF AND ANTIPIRETICLIF

When patient symptoms such as fever or pain, such as tablet "Paracetamol" motor "Nurofen" juice "Naiz" hits.

It should be noted that treatment with such a drug should not last more than five days. The main purpose of these funds is to relieve the symptoms, but they do not affect the infection and inflammation.

IMMUNOMODULATORS

Regardless of the symptoms of chronic endometritis and the response of patients to treatment, for example, tablets "Immudon" for Echinacea extract, it is definitely necessary to take drugs for the development of immune protection.

The body's natural defense function is greatly reduced during inflammation, and you will not be able to fight your own infection.

ADDITIONAL FUNDS

Depending on the age and condition of the patient, additional treatment may be recommended. The doctor prescribes a course of health treatment to correct chronic endometritis. treated as follows, is considered a positive past date.

In most cases, women are recommended mud, radon baths and physiotherapy courses. These methods are aimed at quick recovery of the whole body and the normalization of the menstrual cycle.

CHRONIC ENDOMETRITIS: TREATMENT OF FOLK MEDICINES

Some of the fair sex do not want to contact the doctor and initiate self-treatment of the disease. It should be noted that this is very dangerous. You will not be able to determine the exact cause of the disease and you can not treat what you need. Nevertheless, there are several popular recipes for the treatment of chronic endometritis and the elimination of its symptoms.

It is necessary to mix all the components in the same ratio and carefully mix the mass as a result. Take two cups of boiling water and take a bath in steep water for about half an hour. Then do not freeze the liquid and use it for cleaning several times a day.

The second way: eucalyptus for the treatment of endometritis pine buds, regular eucalyptus, leaves of berries, you will need the following dried plants, medicinal alfalfa and meadowsweet flowers to prepare this car. Mix the good ingredients carefully and in equal proportions.

After that, take one teaspoon of empty material and fill it with two glasses of boiling water. put the life in a water bath and wait an hour. Then do not freeze the broth and wait for it at room temperature.

The final solution should be filled in the bulb and once a day before going to bed vaginal washing routine should be done.

It should be mentioned that this herb not only reduces the inflammation of the genital organs, but also has a beneficial effect on the normalization of blood concentration and the production of female hormones. It perfectly strengthens the immune system and helps cleanse the body of toxins, and it is also delicious.

It is recommended that the course of treatment lasts six months. At this time, you will be quite all in one set of medicine.

This vehicle is also useful for the body of a woman who has chronic endometritis. the answer about it is only good. You can buy medicine at any pharmacy chain.

To collect the broth, you need to take two tablespoons and fill them with boiling water in a ratio of one to one. After that, wrap the solution and let it stand for several hours. Next, strain the broth through cheesecloth and wait for it.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Do not forget that it is necessary to consult a doctor before treatment with folk medicine. Perhaps he will prescribe this drug and herbal tea as a further correction to the main treatment.

This procedure can lead to the entry of pathogenic microorganisms into the fallopian tubes and ovaries, and in some cases, the doctor may strictly prohibit the practice of syringing various herbs. In this case, you need to treat not only chronic endometritis, but also salpingitis (inflammation of the fallopian tubes), and adnexitis (inflammation of the ovaries).

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